

aldehyde, also furnished the related 3-aminocoumarin derivatives. The present method can be used as a preparative process for 3-aminocoumarin derivatives.

Methyleneamino-acetonitrile condenses with phenols (phenol, β -naphthol, *p*-cresol, *m*-cresol) to furnish diarylmethanes *via* the related aminonitriles, thus :

The reaction can be stopped at the intermediate stage and the aminonitrile can be isolated whence the related amino-acid (IV : COOH in place of CN) could be obtained by hydrolysis with acids.

EXPERIMENTAL

Condensation of Methyleneamino-acetonitrile with Paraformaldehyde: Formation of Serine.—A warm solution of methyleneamino-acetonitrile (3 g. in 30 c.c.) was mixed with a solution of paraformaldehyde (1.5 g.) in alcohol, the latter being made with the help of a few drops from a solution of sodium ethoxide (from 1.15 g. of Na). The temperature was maintained at 50°-60° and the balance of ethoxide solution added in about 10 minutes. The solution was cooled to 40° and left for 12 hours at this temperature. The solution was then made just acidic with acetic acid and concentrated to half its volume in vacuo. On cooling to 10°, a white crystalline deposit separated. This was collected, washed and recrystallised from absolute ethanol, m.p. 64°, yield 2.5 g. (Found: N, 28.6. Calc. for C₄H₆ON₂: N, 28.5 per cent). This substance is (II: R=H).

The above product (2.5 g.), dissolved in the least amount of water, was treated with 2 molar equivalents of 10% H₂SO₄ and the mixture warmed on the steam-bath. Excess of sulphuric acid was removed with BaCO₃ and the solution concentrated gently on the steam-bath. The separated crystalline deposit was recrystallised from

minimum of water, when *dl*-serine (colorless crystals) separated (yield 2.0 g.), m.p. and mixed m. p. with an authentic sample, 246°.

When a large-scale preparation involving kilogram quantities was made, certain minor changes in the condition had to be introduced.

Synthesis of dl-Threonine.—Methyleneamino-acetonitrile (3.4 g.) in absolute alcohol (30 c.c.) was treated with paraldehyde (2.2 g.) in absolute ethanol. To the mixture was added a solution of ethoxide made from Na (1.15 g.) After incubating the solution at 40° for 12 hours, it was concentrated in vacuo. On cooling at 0°, a faint yellow solid separated. This was collected and hydrolysed with HCl on a steam-bath. The p_H of the solution was adjusted to the isoelectric point of threonine, when it separated in colorless crystalline form. Recrystallised from methanol it had m.p. 229° (decomp.), and was identified as *dl*-threonine (III : R = Me) by direct comparison and by R_f value; yield 70%.

Condensation of p-Anisaldehyde with Methyleneamino-acetonitrile: Formation of α -Cyano- α -methyleneamino- β -p-methoxyphenylethylene (III B:R' = p-methoxyphenyl).—The condensation was carried out essentially as described for threonine, using the same molar quantities. After reduction of volume, a bright yellow product separated on cooling which was crystallised from 80% ethanol, m.p. 126°, yield 70%. (Found: N, 15.02. Calc. for $C_{11}H_{10}ON_2$: N, 15.05 per cent). The above product was hydrolysed with 15% HCl at 100°, and on removing the excess of HCl with sodium acetate (p_H of solution ca. 5.5), it crystallised in fine colorless needles, m.p. 155°. (Found: N, 7.4. $C_{10}H_{11}O_3N$ requires N, 7.2 per cent). It is α -amino- β -p-methoxyphenylacrylic acid. The above acid was dissolved in water with least amount of NaOH solution and reduced with excess of 2½% sodium amalgam. The p_H of the solution was adjusted to 5.5, and on concentration it afforded *dl*-tyrosine, m.p. and mixed m.p. 290° (decomp.), yield 60% of theory.

Similarly, in the above experiment, when piperonal replaced anisic aldehyde, the intermediate product (IV : R' = 3:4-methylenedioxy-phenyl) was obtained in 80% yield. Recrystallised from hot benzene in bright yellow needles it had m. p. 220°. (Found: C, 66.2; H, 4.3; N, 14.2. $C_{11}H_8O_2N_2$ requires C, 66.0; H, 4.0; N, 14.0 per cent).

The above compound (4.0 g.), suspended in water, was hydrolysed with 15% HCl (60 c.c.) till the whole passed into solution. The solution was then adjusted to about p_H 4 and concentrated, when the acrylic acid (3.7 g.) separated. The colorless acid was recrystallised from hot water, m.p. 127°. (Found: N, 6.8. $C_{10}H_8O_4N$ requires N, 6.7 per cent).

The above acid was reduced with sodium amalgam and the related saturated acid was isolated *via* the copper salt. Recrystallised from hot water it had m.p. 238°. [Found: N, 6.65. Calc. for $C_{14}H_{11}O_4N$ (amino-3:4-methylenedioxyphenylpropionic acid): N, 6.6 per cent],

The related veratric aldehyde product furnished the intermediate (IV : R' = 3:4-dimethoxyphenyl), m.p. 172°. (Found: C, 66.5; H, 5.9; N, 13.1. $C_{12}H_{12}O_4N_2$ requires C, 66.6; H, 5.6; N, 13.0 per cent). The related α -amino- β -3:4-dimethoxyphenylacrylic acid had m.p. 143° after crystallisation from hot, very dilute ethanol. (Found: N, 6.4. Calc. for $C_{11}H_{13}O_4N$: N, 6.3 per cent).

Condensation of Methyleneamino-acetonitrile with Salicylaldehyde: Formation of 3-Aminocoumarin.—A solution of salicylaldehyde (6.1 g.) and methyleneamino-acetonitrile (3.4 g.) in glacial acetic acid was saturated with HCl at 0° and left at that temperature for 12 hours. The bright red deposit was collected and hydrolysed by refluxing with HCl. After dissolution in sodium hydroxide solution and reprecipitation, the yellow-coloured product was crystallised from dilute alcohol in tiny needles, m.p. and mixed m.p. with an authentic sample, 127-28°. Acetyl derivative, m.p. 201°, yield 5.6 g. When *o*-methoxysalicylaldehyde (1:2:3) (7.6 g.) replaced salicylaldehyde in the above experiment, the related 8-methoxyaminocoumarin, m.p. 201°, was obtained in 60% yield. (Found: N, 7.4. $C_{11}H_9O_3N$ requires N, 7.3 per cent.). Similarly β -resorcylic aldehyde afforded 7-hydroxy-3-aminocoumarin, m.p. > 260° in similar yield. (Found: N, 8.1. $C_9H_7O_3N$ requires N, 7.9 per cent.).

Condensation of p-Cresol with Methyleneamino-acetonitrile.—*p*-Cresol (5 g.) was added to a solution of KOH (2 g.) in minimum of water and the solution was buffered to p_H 9. Methyleneamino-acetonitrile (3.2 g.) in absolute ethanol (25 c.c.) was added to the above and the mixture refluxed for 1 hour. After removal of most of the alcohol in vacuo, the mixture was made acidic with acetic acid, when an oil separated from which a white crystalline solid, m.p. 192°, was obtained and it was identified as a polymer of methyleneamino-acetonitrile. The residual thick oil was hydrolysed with HCl and the acid solution on concentration gave the hydrochloride of β -*p*-homocresylaminoacetic acid (IV:COOH in place of CN), m.p. 243°. (Found: N, 6.3. Calc. N, 6.0%). Similarly *m*-cresol in the above experiment afforded the related amino-acid hydrochloride, m.p. 209°. (Found: N, 6.6. Calc. N, 6.0%).

When a mixture of methyleneamino-acetonitrile (1.7 g.), β -naphthol (3.6 g.) and KOH (1.4 g.) in alcoholic solution (20 c.c.) was refluxed on steam-bath for 2 hours and left overnight, a crystalline deposit (0.5 g.), m.p. 192°, separated which was identified as the polymer of the aminonitrile. The alkaline solution on acidification with acetic acid gave a pale pink solid, m.p. 203° after crystallisation. It was identified as dihydroxydianaphthylmethane. (Found: C, 83.4; H, 5.6. $C_{21}H_{16}O_2$ requires C, 84.0; H, 5.3 per cent). The diacetyl derivative had m.p. 215° (cf. Hosans, *Ber.*, 1892, 25, 3214).

In the above experiment the solution of the reactants was buffered to p_H 9 and the mixture warmed to 80° for 6 hours and then the alcohol was removed in vacuo. On acidification with acetic acid a semi-solid separated which was hydrolysed with 15% HCl on steam-bath. From the acidic solution the hydrochloride of *p*-2-hydroxy-homonaphthylaminoacetic acid was isolated, m.p. 223° (formula analogous to IV). (Found: N, 5.5. Calc. N, 5.2%).

Methyleneamino-acetonitrile in a blank experiment did not decompose to formaldehyde under the conditions of the above experiments and therefore the formation of diarylmethanes was not due to the direct reaction of liberated formaldehyde with the phenols. Moreover, the isolation of intermediate glycine derivatives is a proof of the correctness of the course of the reaction depicted.